

Ancient Near Eastern Kingship and the Royal Son of Psalm 2

For modern people, kingship belongs to the misty realms of ancient history, or theatrical presentations of British monarchs such as Victoria, Elizabeth, or even King Henry VIII. But kings and their kingdoms permeate the pages of Scripture from the small warring kings of Genesis 14 with whom Abraham fought to the empire-wide authority of such figures as Ashurbanipal and Nebuchadnezzar to maniacal despots such as Antiochus Epiphanes IV and King Herod the Great. We must look closely at the role of kings in the ancient world to understand our Bible and the hope we maintain for the kingdom of God. In this paper, we will look at Psalm 2, one of the great royal, Messianic psalms. We will look at it within its cognitive environment and the practices of ancient Near Eastern kingship.

John Walton has ably described kingship in his text, *Ancient Near Eastern Thought and the Old Testament*. Kingship comes from heaven. The king stood between the divine and human realms and mediated the power of the deity to his city and beyond. To do this, he needed to discern the divine will by being privy to their council through divination and prophetic oracles. In carrying out the divine will, the king would maintain justice, protect the vulnerable, and lead warriors into battle lest his people and the land descend into chaos. He initiated building projects such as canals, city walls, and temples to his patron god. He would ensure that the temple cult was correctly performed to keep the gods pleased and favorable to him and his people.¹

B.P. Irwin explains that

... [I]n the ancient world, the administration of justice was a royal responsibility that was exercised by virtue of the monarch's connection with the divine realm. In Egypt the Pharaoh was understood to be the incarnation of the god Horus with responsibility for upholding *maat*, the standard of divine "truth" or "justice" without which society could not function.... In the law code instituted by Hammurabi of Babylon (1792-1750 BC),

¹ John H. Walton, *Ancient Near Eastern Thought and the Old Testament: Introducing the Conceptual World of the Hebrew Bible*, Baker Academic, Grand Rapids, MI, 2006, 278-286.

the gods Anu and Enlil are said to have elevated the king to the throne with the responsibility to “make justice prevail in the land, to abolish the wicked and the evil, [and] to prevent the strong from oppressing the weak” (*COS* 2.131:336).²

Kingship was pervasive in the ancient world, and not in Egypt and Mesopotamia only, as one might expect. “From the conquest onwards, all the peoples with whom Israel came into contact had kings. [The] ... Edomites, Moabites, and Ammonites, who conquered their own territories during the same period as Israel, went over to government by a national monarchy soon after their settlement.”³

Israel, however, held out for two centuries despite harassment and sometimes domination from other nations. After Gideon conquered the Midianites, the grateful Israelites asked him to rule over them with his sons,⁴ “Be our king and your family can be a dynasty.” But Gideon refused. This can only be because of his conviction that YHWH was Israel’s king and to appoint a human king would be to turn from faith in Yahweh’s protection and provision.⁵ Yet, the continued pressure from surrounding nations caused Samuel to relent when the people demanded a king. When Samuel inquired of the Lord, the Lord said, “They have not rejected you, but they have rejected me.”⁶ Saul became Israel’s first king, and within a generation, David and his family would replace him and begin the Davidic line of kings in Israel and Judah.

² B.P. Irwin, *Dictionary of the Old Testament Prophets*, “Social Justice,” IVP Academic, Downers Grove, IL, 2012, 722.

³ B. Clappert, *The New International Dictionary of New Testament Theology*, “King, Kingdom,” Vol 2, Zondervan, Grand Rapids, MI, 1979, 373.

⁴ See Judges 8:22-23.

⁵ Matthews and Benjamin point out that elders were responsible to protect and provide for a village and kings had the same twofold responsibility for the state. See Victor H. Matthews and Don C. Benjamin, *Social World of Ancient Israel*, “The Elder,” 121-131 and “The Monarch,” 159-175, Hendrickson Publishers, 1993.

⁶ I Samuel 8:7.

With this background, we turn to Psalm 2. As we examine the text, we will find our understanding of it enriched in the light of ancient kingship in the Near East.

Bruce K. Waltke provides helpful background information to the placement of this psalm in the Psalter.

1. All Psalms in Book 1 have superscripts except for 10 which was joined to 9 in the Hebrew text and 33 which was joined to 32, and Psalms 1 and 2. This has led commentators to see 1 and 2 as an introduction to the book.
2. 1:1a begins with אֲשֶׁר and 2:12c begins with אֲשֶׁר suggesting these as an inclusio unifying the two chapters.
3. The introduction of 1:2 uses הִשְׁתַּחֲוֶה , *to meditate*; 2:1 uses the same word for *to plot*.
4. The last verses of each use דֶּרֶךְ , *way or road*, as a metaphor with אָבֵד , *perish*.
5. Both use “mock” – לְעֵצָה in 1:1 of those who mock against the law and לְעֵצָה , the Lord mocking the rebels.
6. The righteous prevail over the wicked in Psalm 1. This is done through the anointed king of Psalm 2 who prevails over the nations.
7. The king’s triumph in Psalm 2 depends upon his obedience to the law (Deut 17:18-19) which is the basis for triumph in Psalm 1.
8. Psalm 2 transitions to the rest of the psalter. The victory is through prayer over certain people in Psalm 3, prayer over officials in Psalm 4, and prayer over all types of evildoers in Psalm 5.⁷

This is more than interesting editorial information. These insights place the Torah *and the King* central to the worship and success of Israel. Israel has come a long way from the days of Gideon, and because Psalm 2 is classified as a coronation psalm,⁸ the establishment of kingship is now part of the liturgy of worship. It is possible, also, that this psalm was performed not just at the accession of a new king, but at the anniversary of his enthronement.⁹ In the ancient Near

⁷ Bruce K. Waltke, CRUX Winter 2007/Vol 43, No. 4, “Ask of Me My Son: An Exposition of Psalm 2,” 2-19, pp. 2-3.

⁸ J. Clinton McCann, Jr., *The New Interpreters Bible Commentary*, Vol IV, Psalms, Abingdon, Nashville, 1996, 689.

⁹ Waltke, 4.

East, kings would regularly legitimize their reign with “prophecies” predicting their coming, or with words of deity affirming their administration.¹⁰

When we add to this the fact that the Jewish New Testament writers quoted from this psalm more than any other,¹¹ we can see its centrality in the minds of God’s people in both Old and New Testament times.¹²

Psalm 2 is a beautifully structured poem consisting of four scenes of three verses each. Scene 1 takes place in foreign courts where nations conspire to overthrow YHWH and his anointed. Scene 2 takes place in the heavenly realm where YHWH speaks against these kings and announces the installation of his king. Scene 3 takes place on Mt. Zion, the locus where the divine and human realms intersect, and where God’s anointed has been enthroned. Scene 4 is the psalmist stepping forth at the coronation to admonish the kings mentioned in 1-3 to submit.¹³ We will follow this outline in the remainder of this paper.

Scene 1 – 2:1-3

¹ Why do the nations conspire, and the peoples plot in vain?

² The kings of the earth rise up and the rulers band together against the LORD and against his anointed, saying,

³ “Let us break their chains and throw off their shackles.”¹⁴

The conspirators are not worthless rabble-rousers. They are kings of vassal states, at one time submitted to the king of Israel, but who see a regime change in Israel as an opportunity to

¹⁰ Walton, 282-283. See his comments on “Rule Through Divine Sponsorship.”

¹¹ Keil & Delitzsch, *Commentary on the Old Testament*, Vol V, Psalms, Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI, 90.

¹² “Psalm 2 is ... quoted either directly or indirectly seven times in the New Testament (Matt. 3:17 [= Mark 1:11; Luke 3:22]; 17:5 [= Mark 9:7; Luke 9:35]; Acts 4:24-26; 13:33; Heb. 1:5; 5:5; Rev. 2:27) and is alluded to at least another five times (John 1:49; Heb. 1:2; Rev. 12:5; 19:15, 19).” George A. Gunn, *Bibliotheca Sacra* 169 (October-December 2012): 427-42, “Psalm 2 and the Reign of the Messiah,” 427.

¹³ Waltke, 3.

¹⁴ All Scripture references are from the New International Version unless otherwise noted.

rebel. This was common in antiquity. A new king could be young and untested. He might be too preoccupied with internal disputes and solidifying his reign against rivals to pay attention to outliers in his realm. Walton notes:

Changes in kingship created political instability. When a change in kingship occurred in a powerful nation, the rulers of lesser nations under its control might take the opportunity to rebel against their new overlord. Frequently, they formed an alliance to rebel together. The Assyrian king Sennacherib, e.g., faced rebellions after his accession to the throne, including an alliance involving Hezekiah, king of Judah, and Marduk-Baladan of Babylonia. In another case, Esarhaddon forced vassal kings to swear allegiance to his son, Ashurbanipal, and promise not to rebel when Ashurbanipal succeeded him.¹⁵

Thus, with Psalm 2 celebrating the coronation of a new king, the vassal kings see this as an opportune moment to throw off the shackles of YHWH and his king. The words, *chains* and *shackles* (v 3) “... elsewhere indicate servanthood (Jer 2:20; 30:8) as well as knowledge of and obedience to the “way of the Lord” (Jer 5:5). But the kings and rulers have no intention of recognizing God’s sovereignty, which ... is exercised through God’s ‘anointed,’ or messiah – the king.”¹⁶

Scene 2 – 2:4-6

**⁴The One enthroned in heaven laughs; the Lord scoffs at them.
⁵He rebukes them in his anger and terrifies them in his wrath, saying,
⁶“I have installed my king on Zion, my holy mountain.”**

The scene shifts to heaven. This is fitting considering the ancient belief that kingship derived from the gods. The first words spoken in response to the rebelling vassals are not from the human king but from the deity who installs the king.

From earliest times in Mesopotamia, it was believed that the gods determined where and upon whom kingship would be placed. King Hammurapi of Babylon (c. 1750 BC) claimed that his kingship came from the council of the gods, and in one inscription he states that the god Shamash granted to him kingship and decreed his supremacy. Egyptian

¹⁵ John Walton, *NIV Cultural Backgrounds Study Bible*, Zondervan, Grand Rapids, MI, 2016, 880.

¹⁶ McCann, 689.

kings likewise received divine proclamation of their status, and some scholars have suggested that the “decree” in Ps 2 refers to a divine proclamation of privileges and duties similar to Egyptian coronations....Perhaps closer in comparison is the covenant relationship set up between Assyrian kings and their gods. One of the Hebrew terms used for a royal covenant (*edut* in Ps 132:12; 2 K 11:12) ... is related to the Assyrian word for the covenant between the Assyrian king and the gods (*adu*; see also Ps 132:11). Since the Hebrew word for “decree” in v. 7 is also associated with this covenant term in 81:4-5 (cf. 10:8-10), the idea of a royal covenant is probably in the background to Ps 2.¹⁷

But we have more than God affirming his choice of a king in this passage.¹⁸ God speaks to these kings. First, he laughs. Then, he mocks them. Then, he speaks to them directly. Joseph Lam has introduced an interesting alternative to the typical translation that God is terrifying these kings. He asks that if they are courageous enough to rebel, why would they be afraid? He argues that the Hebrew word in 2:5 for *terrifies* carries the idea of *disinheriting*. “A number of elements in the psalm are suggestive of a legal court context for imagining the relationships between Yahweh, the Judean king, and the foreign rulers.”¹⁹ He argues that this word is based on Hittite legal proceedings and is used this way in Job 1:6; 2:3; and 33:5. The picture the psalmist paints is a legal dispute before a palace court. In this court session, YHWH laughs and mocks these kings. Their suit is without merit. He dismisses their case and disinherits them.

YHWH ... issues a ruling affirming the king of Zion as a true son and the preferred heir. He “dismisses,” indeed “excludes,” the other rulers of the earth from a share in his inheritance, and instead offers his anointed all of the land that would have belonged to these other kings. Analogous to a father who possesses the legal right to apportion his estate to whichever of his sons he pleases, YHWH chooses his son in Zion to be the sole recipient of the earthly inheritance of the nations.²⁰

¹⁷ Walton, 2016, 880.

¹⁸ It should be noted that official theology was not a deity affirming and rewarding the diplomatic skill or victorious warfare of a chieftain who seized power. Instead, the deity took the initiative and made the choice of a king, “often phrased in terms of predetermined divine election.” See Walton, 2006, quoting M. deJong Ellis, “Observations on Mesopotamian Oracles and Prophetic Texts,” 281.

¹⁹ Joseph Lam, *Vetus Testamentum* 64 (2014) 3446, “New Light from the Ugaritic Legal Text RS 94.2168;” 35.

²⁰ *Ibid.*, 44.

Finally, we see that YHWH establishes his king on Mt. Zion. Waltke explains the significance of this location.

(YHWH) chose a mountain as the site of his earthly residence in order to communicate truth about himself in the cultural language of ancient Israel. In that world, temples were located on mountains to symbolize the victory of the local deity over the forces of chaos. Thus the mountain represented the whole creation.²¹

Scene 3 – 2:7-9

⁷ I will proclaim the LORD’s decree: He said to me, “You are my son; today I have become your father.

⁸ Ask me, and I will make the nations your inheritance, the ends of the earth your possession.

⁹ You will break them with a rod of iron; you will dash them to pieces like pottery.”

The scene shifts back to earth. The speaker is no longer YHWH but his appointed king. Yahweh had stern words for the rebelling vassals. He has different words for his elect king, and the king tells us what they are, “You are my Son.” But what did this mean in the ancient Near East? Ancient Egyptians believed the king to be the son of the gods and therefore divine. Mesopotamian texts considered the king to be human but adopted and nurtured by the gods.

Although the king in Mesopotamia was figuratively portrayed as being born, nurtured and nursed by goddesses, the metaphor of relationship was understood in terms of election and decree to kingship. The Assyrian king Esarhaddon is told that the goddess Ishtar is both his father and his mother. In similar fashion, Ashurbanipal declares that he was raised by his goddess, who gave him kingship and ordained eternal life for him. But Assyrian kings were never described with divine titles or worshiped as in Egypt.²²

Israelite theology moved the king even further from deity. He was not divine and was not nurtured physically by YHWH, but he was adopted on the day of his coronation. We can chart it this way.

²¹ Waltke, 8.

²² Walton, 2016, 881.

Egyptian	Mesopotamian	Israelite
The king was divine	The king was not divine but nurtured by the gods.	The king was not divine or physically nurtured by God but was adopted as a “son.”

This understanding in Israel would also blend with the idea that Israel was God’s son, and the king, as the representative Israelite, was *the son, par excellence*. As God’s son, the king is now given his first gift of grace. He is told to ask God for something – “Ask of me.” One thinks of Solomon’s dream after his coronation when God said, “Ask for whatever you want me to give you.”²³ Walton provides several examples of this practice in antiquity.

Dream narratives are common in ancient Near Eastern literature, especially among kings facing new challenges. Thus, King Gudea of Mesopotamia (third millennium BC) received instruction to build a temple to Ningirsu and place the statues of the deity inside, the Egyptian pharaoh Netjer-er-khet was warned of impending famine, Amenhotep II received battle plans from the god Amon, and King Kirta of Ugarit gained instruction for conquest and personal restoration from the deity.²⁴

At the coronation, God invites the king to ask for anything and gives the boundaries of the request – the ends of the earth – in other words, anything you want. But we must see this as more than, “I’ll give you anything.” Some have viewed the promise of “the ends of the earth” to be nothing more than palace hyperbole. We must see it in the context of God’s covenants with Israel and Abraham where he promised that through this man and the nation he would bless all the families of the earth. God’s plan was always one of world dominion. He was not content with the little piece of real estate between the great world empires of Egypt and Mesopotamia.

To be sure, Psalm 2 can be treated simply as an example of ancient Near Eastern royal ideology with its characteristic tendency toward hyperbole. But Psalm 2 was preserved by the community faith as something more than a historical artifact of the Davidic dynasty. In periods of monarchical weakness and even after the disappearance of the

²³ I Kings 3:5.

²⁴ Walton, 2016, 563-564.

monarchy, Psalm 1 was preserved and treasured as Israel's poetic answer to the fundamental question, who rules the world? And the answer is clear: The Lord reigns!²⁵

This king will break or rule the nations with a rod of iron and shatter them like earthenware. Clappert says that “defeating enemies with a scepter, originally a club-like weapon of war, was a common image for ancient Near Eastern kings”²⁶ and dashing them like pottery calls to mind Egyptian kings inscribing curses on pottery jars and then smashing the jars, thus invoking the curse.²⁷

Scene 4 – 2:10-12

¹⁰ Therefore, you kings, be wise; be warned, you rulers of the earth.

¹¹ Serve the LORD with fear and celebrate his rule with trembling.

**¹² Kiss his son, or he will be angry and your way will lead to your destruction,
for his wrath can flare up in a moment. Blessed are all who take refuge in him.**

The last words of the psalm are now spoken. The psalmist steps forth and addresses the rebelling vassals. They are to cease their foolish ways. They should serve the king of Israel, the representative of YHWH. Waltke notes that “vassal kings in the Ancient Near East kissed the ground immediately before the feet of the Overlord’s representative.”²⁸ Just as people who meditate on YHWH’s law day and night are blessed, so now, those who submit to YHWH’s king are blessed.

The introduction of the Psalter is complete with the dual authority of the Law and the King in place. The imagery for Psalm 2 deploys Ancient Near Eastern motifs, but its theology is distinctly Israelite and rooted in God’s covenant to Abraham and Israel to restore God’s

²⁵ Ibid., 690.

²⁶ Clappert, 882.

²⁷ Ibid., 882.

²⁸ Waltke, 13.

dominion on earth. What was practiced at coronations and perhaps at yearly anniversaries of coronations became a promise of something far greater. A promise is certainly what Israel often needed.

Often these (promises) do not fit in with the situation in Judah. The most striking are the promise of world-dominion to the king of Judah.... The discrepancy between the actual situation in the puny kingdom of Judah-Jerusalem and the claim to world-dominion advanced in the Royal Ps. cannot be explained merely in terms of dependence on contemporary notions nor in terms of the fulsomeness of courtly style. Such a clash of claim and reality would be astonishing in Judah-Jerusalem. Israel's unique belief in God plays a decisive role here. The Israelite is permeated by the concept that God is the mightiest of all gods. But it is not enough to believe this. This power of Yahweh has to be manifested.²⁹

And manifested it was one day when an angel appeared to a young virgin in Galilee and announced,

³¹You will conceive and give birth to a son, and you are to call him Jesus. ³²He will be great and will be called the Son of the Most High. The Lord God will give him the throne of his father David, ³³and he will reign over Jacob's descendants forever; his kingdom will never end. (Luke 1:31-33)

It is clear that the writer of Psalm 2 lived in the ancient world of kingship and used the expressions and practices of his time to speak of the unique theology of Israel; one day the true king of heaven and earth would come, and God's dominion on earth would be restored.

²⁹ Franz Hesse, *Theological Dictionary of the New Testament*, Vol IX, "Royal Psalms," Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI, 1981, 505-506.

Bibliography

- Clappert, B. *The New International Dictionary of New Testament Theology*, “King, Kingdom,” Vol 2, Zondervan, Grand Rapids, MI, 1979.
- Gunn, George A. “Psalm 2 and the Reign of the Messiah,” 427-442, *Bibliotheca Sacra* 169 (October-December 2012).
- Hesse, Franz, *Theological Dictionary of the New Testament*, Vol IX, “Royal Psalms,” Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI, 1981.
- Irwin, B.P., *Dictionary of the Old Testament Prophets*, “Social Justice,” IVP Academic, Downers Grove, IL, 2012.
- Keil & Delitzsch, *Commentary on the Old Testament*, Vol V, Psalms, Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI.
- Lam, Joseph, “New Light from the Ugaritic Legal Text RS 94.2168;” *Vetus Testamentum* 64 (2014).
- Matthews, Victor H. and Benjamin, Don C., *Social World of Ancient Israel*, “The Elder,” 121-131 and “The Monarch,” 159-175, Hendrickson Publishers, 1993.
- McCann, Jr., J. Clinton, *The New Interpreters Bible Commentary*, Vol IV, Psalms, Abingdon, Nashville, 1996.
- Steyn, Gert J., “Psalm 2 in Hebrews,” 262-282, *University of Pretoria*, Pietermaritzburg. South Africa, April 2003.
- Waltke, Bruce K., “Ask of Me My Son: An Exposition of Psalm 2,” *CRUX* Winter 2007/Vol 43, No. 4, 2-19.
- Walton, John H., *Ancient Near Eastern Thought and the Old Testament: Introducing the Conceptual World of the Hebrew Bible*, Baker Academic, Grand Rapids, MI, 2006.
- _____, *NIV Cultural Backgrounds Study Bible*, Zondervan, Grand Rapids, MI, 2016,